

A7. How experienced do you estimate you are with the following maintenance tasks?

	1 - very inexperienced	2	3	4	5 - very experienced
Bug fixing	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Maintenance of pull requests	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Code review	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Working with issue trackers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Preparing/performing software releases	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Writing software documentation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Communicating with contributors	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Communicating with users	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Continuous integration	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section B: Years of experience

In this section we ask you about your years of experience.

B1. For how many years have you been programming?

If you don't know the exact number of years, please estimate.

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B2. For how many years have you been programming in a team of 3 or more people (including non-programmers)?

If you don't know the exact number of years, please estimate.

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Section C: Projects

In this section we ask you about the software projects you have worked on.

C1. How many open source projects have you worked on as a *core contributor or maintainer*?

	0	1	2-5	> 5
Number of projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C2. How large were the software projects you have worked on typically?

Please estimate the typical size measured in lines of code (LOC).

If you haven't worked on any software projects yet, please pick the answer n/a.

	< 900 LOC	900-40000 LOC	> 40000 LOC	n/a
Typical project size	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section D: Education

In this section we ask you about your education.

D1. What is your highest degree in computer science or a related field?

	None	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Undergraduate (pursuing a first academic degree)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Bachelor or similar (e.g., German Vordiplom, BSc, BA, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Master or similar (e.g., German Diplom, MSc, MA, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Doctoral degree (PhD, Dr. rer. nat., Dr.-Ing, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section E: Personal information

In this section, we ask you details about yourself.

E1. Have you been given a participant code? If so, please provide it here.

Leave this field empty if you don't have a code. This will not affect the recording or processing of your data.

The participant code is used purely for matters of administration and will not be published.